

ATMOSPHERIC INSTABILITY ASSESSMENT REPORT

National Observatory of Athens

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FLAME is a research project carried out at the Institute for Environmental Research and Sustainable Development (IERSD) of the National Observatory of Athens (NOA). The overarching goal of the project is the study and characterization of the environmental conditions that promote extreme wildfires in Greece, intending to increase awareness and enhance the preparedness of fire operatives and the public.

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1. Introduction

This report summarizes the **knowledge gained** from the study of the 2021 extreme pyroconvective wildfire event in Varympompi (Attica), with particular emphasis on **assessing the role of atmospheric instability in the occurrence of extreme fire behavior**. It presents and discusses results from **numerical simulations** of this event conducted with the **WRF-SFIRE coupled fire-atmosphere** modeling system.

Section 2 of this report provides context information on the examined extreme wildfire event, while Section 3 introduces background pyroconvection theory. Section 4 describes the model and its setup for simulating the wildfire event. Results are presented in Section 5.

2. Context

The wildfires that burned across Greece during the 2021 fire season were unprecedented in intensity, extent, and impact. The largest events occurred in early August 2021 in Attica, Euboea, Elis, Messenia, and Laconia (Fig. 1). According to the European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS), these five wildfire events consumed a total area of approximately 94,000 ha corresponding to almost 75 % of the 2021 annual burned area. Widespread and persistent violent pyroconvection developed in each event of August 2021, denoting conditions highly conducive to strong fire-atmosphere coupling. As a result, all events exhibited extreme fire behavior, characterized by rapid and unpredictable fire spread, massive spotting, and the formation of pyroclouds (see inset photos in Fig. 1).

Figure 1. The extreme pyroconvective events of early August 2021 in Greece.

The Varympompi (Attica) wildfire broke out in the early afternoon hours of August 3 at the foothills of the Parnitha mountain, only a few kilometers north of the center of Athens and very close to the densely populated northern suburbs of the city (flame icon, Fig. 2). This fire event evolved in two phases, burning more than 8,000 ha. The first phase of the event lasted less than 15 hours, from ignition on August 3 to the initial containment on August 4. In this phase, the fire consumed almost 1,000 ha of land (dark red shades, Fig. 2). Following the initial containment on August 4, the fire resurged on August 5, progressing to the north and west and burning an additional 7,500 ha in about two days.

Figure 2. The Varympompi wildfire and associated burned areas.

3. Background theory

Pyroconvection is a common behavioral feature of large and often extreme wildfires. The formation of pyroclouds is as much an atmospheric phenomenon as a process related to the fire itself. The intense heat released by the fire warms the air and forces it to begin rising. As the warm air rises, cooler air begins flowing toward the fire, creating a feedback loop that tends to enhance the intensity of burning. At higher altitudes, the rising warm air begins to cool and expand due to the decreasing atmospheric pressure. As soon as it is cooled enough, water vapor in the rising plume begins condensing on ash particles, eventually leading to the formation of a cumuliform cloud just above the smoke plume. This cloud is called a pyrocumulus, and if the intensity of the burning fire is sufficiently large, it can continue developing into a pyrocumulonimbus. These clouds are similar in structure to storm clouds and can significantly

jeopardize the safety of firefighting crews since they are associated with strong and gusty winds and dense spotting over long distances.

It is worth noting at this point that not all wildfires can potentially create pyroclouds. In particular, the formation of pyroclouds requires three ingredients, all linked to the **vertical structure of the atmosphere**. First, the near-surface conditions need to be warm and dry enough to sustain the intense burning of fuels. Second, the lowest layer of the troposphere, just above the fire, needs to be relatively deep, dry, and unstable, with minimum wind shear. Third, the upper layer of the troposphere, where condensation takes place, needs to be sufficiently moist to support and enhance the buoyancy of the rising smoke plume.

The occurrence of pyroconvection indicates clearly that a wildfire is generating its own weather. The local-scale atmospheric circulation associated with pyroconvective wildfires is often characterized by violent updrafts and downdrafts, significant intensification of surface winds, and prolific spotting over long distances. As the formation of pyroclouds is directly linked to atmospheric stability (which, in turn, is subject to a daily cycle), the collapse of these clouds can result in erratic fire spread through the ignition of new spot fires and the intensification of the surface winds that drive the movement of the fire fronts.

4. Methods

4.1. The WRF-SFIRE modeling system

We used the WRF-SFIRE model to simulate the Varympompi wildfire event. WRF-SFIRE is a coupled fire-atmosphere modeling system¹. It combines a state-of-the-art numerical weather prediction (NWP) model, namely the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model², with a two-dimensional fire spread model, namely SFIRE³. WRF-SFIRE is a quasi-physical model since it resolves the physics of the atmosphere-fire interactions but does not consider the chemistry of fire spread. Instead, fire spread is simulated with the semi-empirical algorithm of Rothermel⁴, which exploits the properties of the burning fuels and terrain and meteorological data for computing the rate of spread (ROS).

¹ Mandel, J. et al. (2011) Coupled atmosphere-wildland fire modeling with WRF 3.3 and SFIRE. *Geoscientific Model Development* 4, 591-610.

² Skamarock, W.C. et al. (2008) A Description of the Advanced Research WRF Version 3. NCAR Technical Note NCAR/TN-475+STR.

³ Mandel, J. et al. (2009) Data assimilation for wildland fires: ensemble Kalman filters in coupled atmosphere-surface models. *IEEE Control Systems Magazine* 29, 47-65.

⁴ Rothermel, R.C. (1972) A mathematical model for predicting fire spread in wildland fuels. Research Paper INT-115, Ogden, UT: US Department of Agriculture, Intermountain Forest and Range Experiment Station.

Contrary to existing operational fire spread models, WRF-SFIRE uses the predicted wind field at the fire line for computing the fire spread, amount of fuels burned, and propagation of the fire front, while a two-way coupling takes place between the fire and the atmosphere. The coupling occurs primarily through the sensible and latent heat fluxes released by the fire. The magnitude of these fluxes is determined by the ROS at the fire perimeter as the latter evolves with time. Therefore, the model's atmosphere “feels” the fire and responds by adjusting air temperature and humidity, density, pressure, and wind. This coupled atmosphere-fire local wind influences fire spread and intensity, thus allowing for a constant feedback loop between the fire and the atmosphere. A technically detailed discussion of the atmosphere-fire coupling in WRF-SFIRE is provided by Mandel et al. (2011)⁵.

4.2. Model setup and numerical experiments

For the simulation of the Varympompi wildfire event, we configured WRF-SFIRE to run from August 3 at 09:00 UTC to August 4 at 03:00 UTC, thus focusing on the first phase of fire spread (i.e., before the initial containment of the event). We conducted numerical simulations on three telescopically nested domains, with horizontal grid spacings of 24.5 km (DO1; mesh size of 120 × 120), 3.5 km (DO2; mesh size of 120 × 120), and 500 m (DO3; mesh size of 120 × 150). In the vertical, 41 unevenly spaced, hybrid, terrain-following sigma-pressure levels are defined, with the model top set to 50 hPa. The default terrestrial datasets distributed with the WRF model⁶ are used for the representation of land use, topography, and soil type. Shortwave and longwave radiation processes are parameterized with the RRTMG (Rapid Radiative Transfer Model) scheme⁷, and the Thompson parameterization⁸ is used for handling microphysics. The Yonsei University Scheme (YSU)⁹ is used to represent the planetary boundary layer, coupled with the revised MM5 scheme¹⁰ for the parameterization of surface-layer processes. Land-surface processes are parameterized with the Unified Noah land surface model¹¹, while convective

⁵ Mandel, J. et al. (2011) Coupled atmosphere-wildland fire modeling with WRF 3.3 and SFIRE. *Geoscientific Model Development* 4, 591-610.

⁶ Skamarock, W.C. et al. (2008) A Description of the Advanced Research WRF Version 3. NCAR Technical Note NCAR/TN-475+STR.

⁷ Iacono, M.J. et al. (2008) Radiative forcing by long-lived greenhouse gases: Calculations with the AER radiative transfer models. *Journal of Geophysics Research*, D13103.

⁸ Thompson, G. et al. (2008) Explicit forecasts of winter precipitation using an improved bulk microphysics scheme. Part II: Implementation of a new snow parameterization. *Monthly Weather Review* 136, 5095-5115.

⁹ Hong, S.Y. et al. (2006) A new vertical diffusion package with an explicit treatment of entrainment processes. *Monthly Weather Review* 134, 2318-2341.

¹⁰ Jimenez, P.A. et al. (2012) A revised scheme for the WRF surface layer formulation. *Monthly Weather Review* 140, 898-919.

¹¹ Tewari, M. et al. (2004) Implementation and verification of the unified NOAH land surface model in the WRF model. In: 20th Conference on Weather Analysis and Forecasting/16th Conference on Numerical Weather Prediction, pp. 11-15.

processes are represented with the Grell-Freitas ensemble scheme¹² in DO1 and DO2 and explicitly resolved in DO3. Meteorology was initialized and driven by the NCEP/GFS operational analyses and forecast data.

The simulation of the wildfire spread was carried out on an ultra-high-resolution modeling domain embedded as a sub-grid in DO3. A grid refinement ratio of 10:1 was adopted, resulting in a fire domain with a horizontal grid spacing of 50 m (mesh size of 1200 × 1200). This particular spatial resolution was chosen based on the resolution of the terrestrial datasets that are available for its initialization. Specifically, these include terrain elevation data, which is used for deriving slope, and fuels data. The 90 m resolution SRTM (Shuttle Radar Topography Mission) data were used for topography. For the representation of fuels, a 20 m resolution prototype fuel map of Greece, derived from the work of Giannaros et al. (2019)¹³, was employed.

To assess the influence of atmospheric instability on fire spread and behavior, we first focused on examining fire-induced winds. For this, we conducted two numerical experiments. The first experiment is highlighted as the control simulation and refers to the deterministic forecasting of fire spread and behavior. The second experiment was carried out by turning off the fire spread model, and its results were exploited for quantifying fire-induced winds in the control simulation, an indicator of the effect of atmospheric instability on fire spread and behavior. Finally, we conducted a third experiment in which we prescribed a weather setup characterized by the absence of atmospheric instability and the dominance of north-easterly winds.

5. Results

5.1. Evaluation of the control simulation

Overall, the control simulation was able to reproduce the main features of the Varympompi wildfire event, including the generally weak northerly winds, the development of fire-induced converging winds ahead of the advancing fire front, nighttime downslope winds driving the southerly propagation of the fire, and also the characteristic smoke plumes. Photographic evidence, shown in Figs. 3 – 5 support the above conclusions. For instance, 30 minutes after ignition, the model successfully reproduced the elliptical growth of the fire (Fig. 3). Two and half hours after ignition, observations indicate a south-westerly propagation of the fire, intense burning along the right flank, and a tilted smoke plume, features that are also present in the control simulation (Fig. 4). Finally, six and half hours after ignition, the control simulation seems

¹² Grell, G.A., and Freitas, S.R. (2014) A scale an aerosol aware stochastic convective parameterization for weather and air quality modeling. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 14, 5233-5250.

¹³ Giannaros, T.M. et al. (2019) IRIS – Rapid response fire spread forecasting system: Development, calibration, and evaluation. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology* 279, 107745.

to reproduce successfully the evening collapse of the planetary boundary layer that resulted in smoke being trapped closer to the ground, as the fire was progressing south-westerly, burning a narrow vegetation band (Fig. 5).

Figure 3. Observed (left) and modeled (right) fire progression and behavior on August 3, 2021, at 11:00 UTC.

Figure 4. Observed (left) and modeled (right) fire progression and behavior on August 3, 2021, at 13:00 UTC.

Figure 5. Observed (left) and modeled (right) fire progression and behavior on August 3, 2021, at 16:30 UTC.

Examination of VIIRS active fire-detection data, shown with the flame icons in Figs. 6 and 7, also supports the generally good agreement between the control simulation and the observed evolution of the fire event. For example, it can be seen that two h after ignition, the model

successfully reproduced the southward fire propagation, underestimating the growth along the left flank and the tail of the fire (Fig. 6), while by the time the fire had progressed to almost its final observed perimeter, it can be seen that the control simulation overestimated fire growth to the west, and underestimated fire growth to the north, at the tail of the fire. Nevertheless, the overall agreement between the modeled and observed fire progression is satisfactory.

Figure 6. Observed (flame icons) and modeled (red shades) fire progression on August 3, 2021, at 12:30 UTC. The black area denotes the final event perimeter.

Figure 7. Observed (flame icons) and modeled (red shades) fire progression on August 3, 2021, at 12:30 UTC. The black area denotes the final event perimeter.

5.2. Fire-induced winds

At 11:00 UTC, 30 minutes after ignition, the magnitude of surface fire-induced winds was between 2 - 3 m/s (Fig. 8, left), which is on the order of the magnitude of ambient winds, while the impact of the fire on vertical velocities was between -1 to +2 m/s (Fig. 8, right). The fire-induced perturbations to the vertical velocity field appear as updrafts along the plume, driving the fire and compensating downdrafts and inflow into the plume, altogether accelerating surface winds leading the fire progression.

Figure 8. Surface (left) and vertical (right) fire-induced winds on August 3, 2021, at 11:00 UTC.

Figure 9. Surface (left) and vertical (right) fire-induced winds on August 3, 2021, at 13:00 UTC.

Two and half hours after ignition, when the ambient winds shifted to north-easterlies and increased in magnitude, we can again see that the presence of the fire accelerates surface winds (Fig. 9, left), with their magnitude now exceeding 5 m/s, again on the order of the magnitude of the prevailing ambient winds. As previously shown, this acceleration is related to the updrafts and downdrafts that the fire generates through the direct heating of the lower atmosphere (Fig.

9, right). These updrafts and downdrafts are further enhanced by the presence of atmospheric instability.

5.3. Fire spread under stable atmospheric conditions

In the previous Section of this report, we showed that the fire-atmosphere coupling favored under conditions of atmospheric instability generates fire-induced winds that play a decisive role in fire spread and behavior. To further support our preliminary conclusions of the important role that atmospheric instability plays in fire spread and behavior, we present in this Section results from the third numerical experiment we conducted with the WRF-SFIRE modeling system.

Figure 10. WRF-SFIRE fire spread maps for the Varympompi wildfire event. The left column presents results under the actual conditions scenario. The right column presents results under a hypothetical scenario of strong north-easterly winds. Each row shows forecasted fire spread 2, 6, and 12 hours following ignition.

A quick look at the fire spread maps of Fig. 10 reveals the important role that atmospheric instability played in the fire spread and behavior of the Varympompi wildfire event. What can be seen is that under a hypothetical weather setup involving strong NE winds and a stable

atmosphere, the fire would not have spread to the extent it did. In particular, a stable atmosphere and strong NE winds would have driven the fire to the southwest, containing its lateral expansion. However, under the light winds that were blowing and in the presence of atmospheric instability, the fire was able to quickly spread in all cardinal directions. Moving an area rich in extremely dry fuels, particularly to the north, the fire sustained intense burning, developed a strong convective column supported by the unstable atmospheric conditions, and eventually evolved into a plume-driven event with extreme fire behavior.

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